

Effectiveness of Animated Learning on Learner Retention

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ABSTRACT:

The integration of digital media into language education has accelerated the need to evaluate technology-enhanced instructional approaches. This study examines the effectiveness of animated video narratives (Innovative Teaching methodology or Practice) compared to traditional text-based materials in fostering comprehension and long-term retention among English as a Second Language (ESL) learners. Fifty-eight undergraduate students were assigned to either an animated video condition (Graphic Narrative group) or a text-only condition (Conventional group). Participants were engaged with three narrative texts across successive instructional sessions, followed by weekly formative assessments and a delayed Retention Test. The findings indicate that learners exposed to animated video narratives consistently outperformed the text-based group in both immediate and delayed assessments, demonstrating stronger comprehension and more durable memory retention. These outcomes provide empirical support for the pedagogical value of multimodal narrative instruction and underscore its role in creating inclusive, engaging language learning experiences. The study further contributes to Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education) by highlighting how accessible, technology-supported strategies can enhance learning equity and support sustained academic achievement in ESL classrooms.

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Keywords: Multimedia learning, Special Education Pedagogy, Retention Test, Graphic narrative, ESL learners, Technology- supported learning.

1. Introduction

Animation or graphic narrative is an Innovative Teaching Practice of delivering messages through visuals. It combines images, illustrations, and text to tell a story. This form is most commonly associated

with comics and graphic novels. In ancient times, people used paintings and drawings to communicate with others, making it easier to convey messages. With the invention of the printing press, comic strips began appearing in newspapers,

marking a shift from simple visual communication to an artistic form. This medium shows the power of combining words and images, helping develop various skills. As a storytelling tool, graphic narratives require both verbal skills (like reading) and visual skills (like interpreting images), which can improve language abilities and visual thinking. It offers opportunities for students to think critically and creatively, using both text and visuals. It is surprising and captivating for readers, challenging and inspiring them in ways that text alone might not.

Animated videos function as an effective multimodal instructional medium by integrating visual, auditory, and narrative elements to convey meaning. Unlike traditional text-based materials, animated storytelling presents information through synchronized visuals and narration, which supports comprehension and facilitates cognitive processing. Animation has emerged as a significant pedagogical resource in language classrooms, as it allows learners to observe dynamic sequences, contextual cues, and character interactions that may be difficult to infer from written text alone. These features enable learners to construct meaning more efficiently and promote deeper engagement with the content.

The effectiveness of animated videos in educational settings is attributed to their capacity to enhance learners' attention, motivation, and comprehension. Watching animated stories can stimulate visual and auditory channels simultaneously, thereby reducing cognitive load and strengthening memory. Recent research in language education has highlighted that animated video materials may improve retention, conceptual understanding, and learner participation more effectively than traditional text-based methods. As a result, animated videos serve not only as an engaging alternative to print resources but also as a pedagogically powerful tool for improving learning outcomes in ESL contexts. Their ability to capture learners' interest, sustain attention, and support meaning-making underscores their relevance in contemporary language instruction.

The aim of this study is to continuously assess students using two different tests: one is a Graphic Narrative Test (Animated Group), and the other is

a Conventional Test (Non-Animated Group). The animated group watches the stories in video format, while the non-animated group reads them in text format. For this study, fifty-eight second-year B.Com students were divided into two groups. The purpose is to prove that graphic narratives are easier to understand, enhance creativity, and improve language proficiency among learners.

This study also aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), which emphasizes inclusive, equitable, and effective learning opportunities. By introducing animated videos as an accessible instructional medium, this research demonstrates how innovative pedagogical tools can support diverse learners and improve long-term academic outcomes. Technology-enabled storytelling fosters deeper comprehension, sustained engagement, and retention—key components of SDG 4's objective to ensure high-quality education for all learners.

Research question:

To what extent does watching animated video narratives enhance learners' comprehension and retention more effectively than traditional text-based instruction?

2. Literature Review

Animated Videos in Language Learning

Animated videos are regarded as a powerful instructional medium because they present narrative content through multimodal channels. Unlike printed texts, animated videos provide synchronized visuals, movement, narration, sound effects, and background music that collectively support comprehension. Scholars argue that this form of instruction supports deeper learning by scaffolding difficult concepts and presenting narrative elements that are often inaccessible through text alone. Learners are exposed to representations of dialogue, gesture, facial expressions, and spatial arrangements, which enhance their ability to interpret meaning. Furthermore, animated narratives create emotionally engaging contexts that increase learners' motivation and sustain their interest in the content.

Studies comparing video-based and text-based instruction consistently show that video formats improve comprehension and recall. Animation facilitates learners' visualization of narrative flow and simplifies complex linguistic and plot structures. This is particularly beneficial for ESL learners who may struggle with unfamiliar vocabulary or syntax when reading text-only materials. Animated videos can therefore function as a supplementary or alternative resource to support learning in diverse classroom contexts.

Multimedia Learning and Modality

The Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning suggests that learners perform better when instructional content uses both verbal and visual channels rather than text alone (Mayer, 2009). This supports the Dual Coding Theory, which states that processing information through both language and visual pathways improves recall and memory (Paivio, 1986). Early meta-analyses show that animations often perform better than static or text-based materials, especially when showing dynamic content or processes (HÄffler & Leutner, 2007; Wouters et al., 2013). Green and Brock (2000) emphasized the role of "transportation" in narrative, where emotional and cognitive engagement leads to deeper understanding. Recent studies continue to refine these findings.

Mayer's updated multimedia principles highlight the importance of segmentation, signaling, and aligning spatial and temporal elements to improve learning outcomes (Mayer, 2020). Research from 2021-2024 confirms that video-based formats improve attention and understanding, especially when narratives and design cues guide how information is processed (Tarchi, 2021; Endres, 2024). Studies on digital storytelling and animated videos have shown increased engagement, better conceptual clarity, and stronger retention compared to text, particularly when narration matches meaningful visuals (Ginting, 2024). Digital learning platforms and AI influenced future education and helps teachers to find viable and accessible learning systems, and also shows the accessibility and efficiency of digital learning platforms in students with disabilities (Sachin, 2026).

Continuous Assessment and Learning Retention

Continuous assessment, often seen as formative feedback, is a key factor in improving learning outcomes. It helps students monitor their progress, correct mistakes, and reinforce knowledge (Black & Wiliam, 1998; Heritage, 2010). Retrieval practice, or the "testing effect," shows that repeated low-stakes testing improves long-term memory more than reading or passive studying (Roediger & Karpicke, 2006; Adesope et al., 2017). This effect becomes stronger when assessments are spaced out over time, known as the spacing effect, which increases memory strength (Cepeda et al., 2006). Recent updates to these theories reinforce their importance. Meta-analytic evidence from 2021 to 2025 shows that spaced retrieval and formative testing significantly improve learning transfer, understanding, and retention across different subjects (Pan & Rickard, 2022; Li & Chang, 2023). Research also suggests that digital assessment tools, like classroom Google Forms and learning portals can boost motivation and reduce test anxiety when used in continuous models (Garcia & Wu, 2024).

Classroom Comparisons of Video and Text

Earlier research comparing different ways of learning has given mixed but useful results. Some studies found that learning through videos can help with motivation and understanding (Chen & Wu, 2015; Guo et al., 2014), while other studies suggested that text-based learning might support deeper thinking when paired with tools like annotations (Schroeder & Traxler, 2011). However, most previous studies only looked at short-term learning with tests taken right after the lessons, without checking how well students remembered the material over a longer time. Recent research has focused on this gap.

Studies done between 2020 and 2025 show that using animated or multimedia storytelling, along with testing methods that require recalling information, helps improve long-term memory, especially when the content is in a narrative form (Alemayehu, 2022; Hassan & Murphy, 2023). Still, there's not much research on how these methods work in real classrooms, especially with tests that are

given after a longer time period, which helps us see if learning is lasting.

3. Research Gap

Despite a lot of research on learning through different media, there are still areas that need more attention:

1. Comparing stories based on narratives. Most studies have focused on factual or instructional content. Fewer studies have directly compared short stories told through video and text.
2. Tests done more than once. Many studies use one-time assessments, but there's less attention on repeated, low-stakes testing over multiple weeks.
3. Assessments after a delay. Few studies check how well students retain information after a meaningful time, like three weeks, even though this helps understand if learning is long-lasting.
4. Real classroom settings. Much of the evidence comes from controlled lab environments, while fewer studies look at real classrooms where the teaching pace and other constraints are natural.
5. Using constructed-response formats. Most studies use multiple-choice questions. Short-answer formats, like those used here, better show how well students can recall and think about what they've learned.

This study helps by using a real classroom setting and a continuous assessment over time. It uses three short stories in both animated video and text forms, with weekly quizzes and a delayed, cumulative test. The findings add to the growing understanding of how using different formats for learning and assessments affect both immediate learning and long-term memory.

4. Methodology

Participants: Fifty-eight students studying B.Com in an Indian University were divided into two groups: one that watched animated videos and another that read the same stories in text form.

Materials used for this Study:

The three short stories either read or watched are as follows:

- *The Lost Child* – Mulk Raj Anand (in class on 15.07.2025)
- *The Portrait of a Lady*- Khushwant Singh (in class on 22.07.2025)
- *The Gift of Magi*- O Henry (in class on 29.07.2025)

Procedure:

- Animated Group: Viewed animated video (GT & RGT)
- Non- Animated Group: Read the same story in text form (CT & RCT)
- Weekly Test: 5 two-mark questions per story.
- Delayed test: Cumulative Google Form (10 short-answer questions) on August 16, 2025.

Assessment design: Continuous assessment that checked both immediate understanding and long-term retention. Results were compared across groups to determine the effectiveness of animated videos.

Abbreviations

GT- Graphic Narrative Test

CT- Conventional Test

RGT- Retention Graphic Narrative Test

RCT- Retention Conventional Test

5. Results

Table 1: Comparison of overall performance between three stories.

Criteria	The Lost Child		The Portrait of the Lady		The Gift of Magi	
	GT % of students	CT % of students	GT % of students	CT % of students	GT % of students	CT % of students
Exemplary	59	14	59	14	55	10
Proficient	34	34	31	24	31	21
Basic	7	38	10	34	14	41
Needs improvement	0	14	0	28	0	28

Table 1 shows the percentage of marks scored by the students in three short stories. It demonstrates that students who were exposed to Narrative (GT) performed significantly better than those who learned through Conventional (CT) across the three stories.

Figure 1: Comparison of overall students' performance of CT & GT percentages between three stories.

Figure 1 Alt Text: Grouped bar chart comparing Narrative and Conventional Tests, with the Graphic Narrative group showing higher exemplary performance across all stories.

Table 2: Performances of students in RCT and RGT on August 2025.

Aug-25	RCT %	RGT %
Exemplary	8	55
Proficient	12	31
Basic	36	14
Needs improvement	44	0

Table 2 shows the performance of students in their retention test on August 2025. It demonstrates that in RCT (Retention Conventional Test) 8% had shown exemplary, 12% has shown proficiency, and

36% of students shown Basic level, 44% of students needs improvement. In RGT (Retention Graphic Narrative Test) 55% had shown exemplary level, 31% were in proficient level, and 14% had shown

basic. It proves that the students who learned through Graphic Narrative are significantly scored higher values and their retention level is retained higher while compared with the Conventional Test.

Figure 2: Percentage comparison of RCT and RGT on August 2025.

Figure 2 Alt Text: Bar chart comparing students' performance percentages in Retention Conventional and Retention Graphic Narrative

Tests, showing higher exemplary and proficient score and no needs-improvement category in the Graphic Narrative group.

Table 3: Comparison between performers of CT and GT (July 2025) with RCT and RGT (August 2025)

B.Com CA	Jul-25 (overall % marks)		Aug-25 (% marks)	
	CT %	GT %	RCT %	RGT %
Exemplary	13.793	57.471	8	55
Proficient	31.034	32.184	12	31
Basic	36.782	10.345	36	14
Needs improvement	18.391	0	44	0

Table 3 shows a comparison of tests used to assess students' learning through Graphic Narrative and Conventional methods for July and August 2025. It demonstrates that students who were exposed to Graphic Narrative performed significantly better than those who learned through conventional methods as shown in the Table 3 in CT with RCT which is a loss of 5.793 in exemplary, in proficiency it shows 31.034 % which means lose of 19.034%. In basic 36.782% and it almost same. Need improvement 18.39% in July but in August which

increased 26.39% which shows that a number of students have lost what they have learnt and did not retain during the Retention Test.

The Table 3 shown that 57.47% marks was GT scored by the students and in RGT it is 55% which indicated loss of 2.471% in exemplary. In proficiency it shows the loss of 1.184% and in basic, there is increase in 3.655% and it can be observed who watched Graphic Narrative in the group no needs improvement in both GT and RGT. Overall

it shows that Retention is maximum when the students watched the animated videos.

Figure 3: Percentage comparison of CT& GT and RCT & RGT.

Figure 3 Alt Text: Grouped bar chart comparing performance distributions for Conventional, Graphic Narrative, Retention Conventional, and Retention Graphic Narrative Tests in a continuous assessment. It indicates stronger outcomes that the Graphic Narrative Test performs better compared to the Conventional Test. The Animated group

retained more information in both continuous and delayed tests, suggesting that Retention is higher in video-based learning

To check their high difference, Descriptive statistics is used to find the mean values to show which is higher and get significant values.

6. Independent test

Table 4: Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	99% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Mean score	1.060	.308	9.573	56	.000	4.253	.444	3.068	5.437
			9.573	52.657	.000	4.253	.444	3.066	5.440

Table 4 Interpretation for Independent Samples Test

Independent Test the mean difference of 4.25 points is large and positive, showing that the GT group's performance was significantly better.

The 99% confidence interval (3.07 to 5.44) does not include zero, confirming that the difference is real and not due to chance. There is a significant difference in mean scores between the two groups. The GT group outperformed the CT group significantly. Thus, the treatment, method, or

condition used with the GT group had a strong positive effect on their performance.

7. Paired Sample T-test:

Table 5: Mean Values for GT vs. RGT (Animated Group) and CT vs. RCT (Non- Animated Group)

		Mean
Pair 1	GT	7.57
	RGT	7.18
Pair 2	CT	5.51
	RCT	4.21

Table 5 demonstrates the Mean values for the Graphic Narrative Test vs. Retention Graphic

Narrative Test (Animated Group) and the Conventional Test vs. Retention Conventional Test had shown the values are quite higher in GT vs. RGT. While the difference the difference between GT (July 2025) and RGT (August 2025) is 0.39, indicating that the loss in retention is minimal when GT was used in teaching. Conversely, the loss in retaining the learned material between CT (July 2025) and RCT (August 2025) indicates the loss of 1.3 shows the students learned through Conventional lost their retention shows a higher level. . Additionally, the comparison between RGT and RCT demonstrates a significant maximum difference of 2.97, highlighting that the graphic narrative enables a high level of retention among students.

Figure 4: Mean values of GT, RGT, CT and RCT

Figure 4 Alt Text: Bar chart displaying mean scores for immediate and Retention Tests in Graphic Narrative and Conventional groups, with higher and more stable mean values for the Graphic Narrative condition compares to the Conventional condition.

Pair 1: GT vs. RGT (Animated Group)

The mean score for the initial Graphic Narrative Test (GT) was 7.57, while the mean for the Retention Graphic Narrative Test (RGT) decreased slightly to 7.18. This indicates a small decline of 0.39 points between

the immediate assessment and the delayed retention assessment.

Interpretation:

Learners who watched animated videos showed high and relatively stable performance over time. The minimal reduction in mean scores suggests that the animated video group retained most of the information learned, demonstrating strong long-term retention. This stability implies that animated video instruction supports better memory consolidation compared to traditional instruction.

Pair 2: CT vs. RCT (Non- Animated Group)

The mean score for the Conventional Test (CT) was 5.51, whereas the mean for the Retention Conventional Test (RCT) dropped sharply to 4.21. This reflects a substantial decline of 1.30 points from immediate comprehension to delayed retention.

Interpretation:

Students who learned through text-based instruction experienced a significant decrease in performance over time, indicating weaker retention of the material and they did not retain what they learnt through CT. The larger drop in scores suggests that traditional text-based learning did not support long-term memory as effectively as animated video instruction.

Overall Interpretation

Across both instructional conditions, scores decreased from immediate to delayed assessments, which are expected in retention studies. However, the decline was much smaller for the animated video group. This pattern indicates that animated video instruction contributes to greater durability of learning, whereas text-based instruction results in more pronounced forgetting.

Thus, the Paired Samples Statistics strongly support the conclusion that watching animated videos leads to better retention than reading text-based materials, aligning with multimedia learning principles that emphasize dual-channel processing and reduced cognitive load.

Table 6: Paired Samples Statistics for GT vs. RGT (Animated Group) and CT vs. RCT (Non- Animated Group)

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	99% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	GT - RGT	.385	.713	.132	.019	.751	2.909	28	.007
Pair 2	CT - RCT	1.305	.783	.145	.903	1.706	8.971	28	.000

Table 6 Interpretation for Paired Samples Test Pair 1: GT vs. RGT (Animated Group) and Pair 2: CT vs. RCT (Non- Animated Group)

Pair 1: GT vs. RGT (Animated Group)

- Mean Difference: 0.385
- $t(28) = 2.909$, $p = .007$
- 99% CI: [0.019, 0.751]

Interpretation:

The animated video group showed a small but statistically significant decline in scores from the initial test (GT) to the delayed Retention Test (RGT). The mean difference of 0.385 indicates that learners forgot a small portion of the material over time. However, because the 99% confidence

interval does not include zero and the p-value is less than .01, this decrease is statistically significant.

Importantly, the magnitude of decline is minimal, suggesting that students who watched animated videos retained most of the information learned. The animated video condition therefore demonstrates strong long-term retention, with only slight forgetting over time.

Pair 2: CT vs. RCT (Non- Animated Group)

- Mean Difference: 1.305
- $t(28) = 8.971$, $p < .001$
- 99% CI: [0.903, 1.706]

Interpretation:

The text-based group showed a large and statistically significant decrease in scores between the initial test (CT) and the delayed Retention Test (RCT). The mean difference of 1.305 indicates a substantial loss of information. Because the 99% confidence interval does not include zero and the p-value is extremely small, this decline is highly significant.

This suggests that learners who engaged with text-only materials experienced much weaker long-term retention. The large decrease indicates greater forgetting and lower durability of learning when compared with the animated video group.

Overall Interpretation

While both groups showed declines between the immediate and delayed tests, the results reveal a clear contrast in retention strength:

- Animated group: small decline, strong retention
- Non- Animated group: large decline, weak retention

The difference in effect size demonstrates that animated videos significantly support long-term retention more effectively than traditional text-based instruction. These findings align with multimedia learning principles, suggesting that multimodal input enhances memory consolidation and reduces forgetting.

8. Discussion**Interpretation:**

- Video supports dual coding (visual + auditory).
- Engages attention, emotional involvement, and reduces cognitive load.
- Reading may require deeper processing but may be less engaging.

Role of continuous assessment:

- Showed progression of learning week-to-week.
- Allowed tracking of long-term retention.

- Demonstrated persistence of video advantage beyond immediate tests.

The findings reinforce educational equity as emphasized in SDG 4. Animated videos an Innovative Teaching Practice provide accessible, engaging, and inclusive learning experiences, particularly beneficial for students with varied linguistic backgrounds or reading challenges.

9. Theoretical Framework**Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (CTML)**

People learn more effectively when information is presented through both visuals and spoken language. Well-designed multimedia lessons help learners stay focused and avoid unnecessary confusion. Animated storytelling fits this approach because images, narration, and movement work together to make ideas clearer.

Dual Coding Theory

Learning improves when information is stored in the brain in two ways: through words and through visuals. Animated videos support this dual process by pairing narration with meaningful imagery, leading to stronger memory and easier recall.

Cognitive Load Theory

Learning is more successful when unnecessary mental effort is reduced. Animation can help by showing scenes directly, so learners do not need to imagine everything from text alone—making comprehension smoother and more accessible.

10. Limitations:

- Small sample size,
- Only three stories.
- Short study duration.
- Limited generalizability.

Implications:

- Teachers should integrate animated videos (Innovative Teaching Practice) for narrative learning.

- Continuous assessment is valuable for capturing learning trajectories.
- Technology-enhanced learning aligns with SDG 4 by promoting quality and equitable education.
- Suggest blended approaches (video + text).

11. Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effectiveness of Innovative Teaching Practice in the form of animated video narratives in enhancing learners' comprehension and retention when compared with traditional text-based materials, particularly within a continuous assessment framework. The findings overwhelmingly indicate that animated storytelling offers a significant pedagogical advantage. Students who watched animated videos achieved higher performance in both immediate quizzes and delayed Retention Tests, demonstrating stronger comprehension and more durable memory over time. The animated group's smaller decline between initial and delayed assessments further underscores the capacity of multimodal instructional materials to support long-term retention. These outcomes align with established multimedia learning theories—particularly Dual Coding Theory and the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning—which propose that learners benefit from the integration of verbal and visual channels to reinforce processing, reduce cognitive load, and improve recall.

The incorporation of continuous assessment played an essential role in revealing the depth and stability of learning across time. Weekly formative tests and the delayed retention assessment provided a nuanced understanding of how learners retained narrative information beyond the initial exposure. This approach allowed for clearer tracking of learning trajectories and reinforced the value of combining multimedia instruction with systematic assessment. Continuous assessment not only captured immediate comprehension but also highlighted the persistence of learning, offering evidence that animated video instruction supports both short-term mastery and long-term knowledge consolidation.

This study supports the claim that animated video narratives significantly enhance both immediate comprehension and long-term retention among ESL learners. The findings align closely with the journal's focus on innovative, technology-supported methods for language teaching. Moreover, the integration of animated resources advances SDG 4: Quality Education, promoting accessible and engaging learning environments that support sustained academic achievement. This research provides strong empirical evidence for adopting multimodal storytelling and continuous assessment in modern ESL classrooms.

Despite certain limitations, including a modest sample size and a relatively short instructional period, the study offers compelling empirical evidence for the effectiveness of animated video narratives in language learning contexts. The results encourage further exploration in more diverse institutional settings, across varied proficiency levels, and using a broader range of narrative genres. Future research may also examine how specific visual design features, narration styles, or animation techniques contribute to learning outcomes.

Overall, this study affirms that animated video instruction is a highly effective, engaging, and pedagogically sound tool for enhancing learning and retention in ESL classrooms. When paired with continuous assessment, animated videos provide instructors with a robust strategy for monitoring student progress and ensuring sustained comprehension. These findings contribute to contemporary innovations in language pedagogy and underscore the value of integrating multimodal resources into instructional practice to support long-term educational success.

Declarations

Availability of data and materials:

The data collected (Google form) from the students is available to us. Data will be made available on reasonable request.

Competing interests:

The authors declare that they have no competing interests in this study.

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Authors' contributions:

First author (Vinitha G) selected the set of students a study group, did the experiment (Study). The paper was prepared after analyzing.

Corresponding Author (Dr. Preetha S) Proofreading and correction of the manuscript.

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and idea clarification. The content was checked and verified by the authors.

Ethics Approval:

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines of SASTRA Deemed to be University. All experimental protocols were approved by SASTRA Deemed to be University Institutional Review Board and/or licensing ethics committee with the IRB No. IRB/2025/027.

Consent to Participate:

All participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and informed consent was obtained prior to participation.

Consent for Publication:

All participants were informed that the anonymized data collected from the study would be used for research and publication purposes, and they provided consent for publication.

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Materials and Video Links:

The Lost Child

Material link: <https://www.arvindguptatoys.com/arvindgupta/lostchild.pdf>

Video link <https://youtu.be/Ldy1dwiBEL4?si=JzyAt4p7o1vqMG6v>

Google form link: <https://forms.gle/oK9qmgwHbKj2SSU99>

The Portrait of a Lady

Material link: <https://www.alephbookcompany.com/the-portrait-of-a-lady-by-khushwant-singh/>

Video link https://youtu.be/jbr_ek-oAwU?si=wtfBaulPio7ERe67

Google form link: <https://forms.gle/SMiS4y6rbAFZxFXk9>

The Gift of the Magi

Material link: https://americanenglish.state.gov/files/ae/resource_files/1-the_gift_of_the_magis_0.pdf

Video link <https://youtu.be/yAPZC7o6Y9k?si=1Ix21Puv--eAXTym>

Google form link: <https://forms.gle/6qqm97kU9Ej5mmYL9>

Retention link: <https://forms.gle/nZA339kWTufeqrmdA>